

Adsorption Studies of Some Aromatic Acids on Silicone Rubber

TRILOCHAN MEDDA, SAMARESH MUKHERJEE and SANTI R. PALIT

Department of Physical Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Jadavpur, Calcutta-32

Manuscript received 15 December 1978, revised 22 September 1978, accepted 27 April 1979

The sorption characteristics of aromatic acids into silicone rubber have been studied with a view to throwing light on solute-polymer interaction. Equilibrium sorption isotherms have been prepared at different temperatures and concentrations to evaluate the degree of sorption. The results reveal that the affinity of the low molecular weight acids for silicone rubber is less than those for higher molecular weight acids. The thermodynamic quantities, viz. standard heats of sorption and standard entropy of sorption values have also been derived. It is suggested that the solute-polymer binding is predominantly of the hydrogen bond type.

WITH the recent advent of unit-dose drug distribution systems in medical applications, plastics are being used at an increasing rate for packaging various dosage forms. Several investigators¹⁻¹⁴ have shown that over extended periods of time preservatives and drugs can be sorbed from solution by plastic materials.

Autian⁹ and his group have clearly established that the plastic of the polyamide type with electronegative polar centres adsorb proton donors such as benzoic acid, phenol and sorbic acid. Recently Palit et al.¹⁵ studied sorption characteristics of phenol and substituted phenols with silicone rubber. They observed that the affinity of the low molecular weight phenols for silicone rubber is less than those of the higher molecular phenols. From the measurement of thermodynamic quantities such as heat of sorption and entropy of sorption they explained the solute polymer binding as predominantly of hydrogen bond type.

The adsorption of drugs by plastics is of concern to pharmacists and to scientists in the health professions in general. Knowledge of the sorption behaviour of a specific plastic material thus would be helpful to the medical science as well as to the industries serving his need. Silicone rubber has been chosen for the present investigation because of its wide use in medical and pharmaceutical applications.

With a view to throw further light on solute-polymer interaction the present investigation was initiated. Studies were made of the sorption characteristic of benzoic acid and substituted benzoic acids, when silicone rubber was used as substrate. Spectral measurements were used to evaluate the solubility coefficient, the enthalpy change and hence the entropy change for the complex formation.

Materials and Methods

Toluic acids and nitrobenzoic acids were obtained as gift sample from B.D.H (England), *m*-aminobenzoic acid and *m*-iodobenzoic acid were obtained from E. Merck, Darmstadt. Salicylic acid, benzoic acid, *p*-isopropyl benzoic acid, chlorobenzoic acids, bromobenzoic acids, *p*-benzoxybenzoic acid used were obtained from Eastman Kodak as gift sample. The acids were recrystallized before use. The solutions were made gravimetrically in double distilled water. The spectral measurements were taken in a Hilger UV spectrophotometer using 1 cm quartz cells at different temperatures (10°, 25°, 40°). Medical grade silicone rubber was obtained as gift from Dow Corning Corporation (Midland, Michigan, U.S.A). The experimental techniques are similar to those discussed in the previous publication¹⁵.

Method of Calculations

The solubility coefficient for each individual compound in the silicone rubber at various temperatures under consideration was calculated as before¹⁵ from the data obtained from these sorption experiments. Table I presents some typical sorption data at three different temperatures. Another relationship often used to express sorption data is the Langmuir equation. To evaluate the saturation value for each of the acids at each temperature, the data were fitted to a form of the Langmuir relationship,

$$\frac{1}{q} = \frac{1}{KSC} + \frac{1}{S} \quad \dots (1)$$

where *q* is the amount of the solute sorbed at equilibrium in moles per 0.25 gm, *K* is a constant, *S* is the saturation value per 0.25 gm, the theoretical amount of solute which the rubber would adsorb

TABLE 1—SORPTION DATA OF AROMATIC ACIDS BY SILICONE RUBBER AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

A. Sorption isotherm					
15°		25°		40°	
$C_L \times 10^6$ M/L	$C_S \times 10^6$ M/O.25 gm	$C_L \times 10^6$ M/L	$C_S \times 10^6$ M/O.25 gm	$C_L \times 10^6$ M/L	$C_S \times 10^6$ M/O.25 gm
p-toluic acid λ_{max} 248 nm					
6.51	1.51	6.71	1.31	6.92	1.11
8.18	1.83	8.46	1.56	8.76	1.28
10.16	2.55	11.28	2.06	11.69	1.65
13.01	3.01	13.41	2.61	14.01	2.03
14.81	3.46	16.63	2.87	15.84	2.42
16.90	3.74	18.48	3.15	17.67	2.46
18.78	4.35	19.52	3.62	20.26	2.89
o-bromo benzoic acid λ_{max} 292 nm					
1.48	0.31	1.55	0.24	1.61	0.22
2.25	0.45	2.32	0.38	2.41	0.32
2.99	0.58	3.07	0.49	3.19	0.39
3.41	0.65	3.48	0.56	3.60	0.47
3.76	0.72	3.84	0.64	3.94	0.55
4.51	0.86	4.62	0.77	4.64	0.61
5.07	0.95	5.19	0.83	5.33	0.70
B. Langmuir isotherm					
15°		25°		40°	
$1/c \times 10^{-3}$	$1/q \times 10^{-3}$	$1/c \times 10^{-3}$	$1/q \times 10^{-3}$	$1/c \times 10^{-3}$	$1/q \times 10^{-3}$
Benzoic acid λ_{max} 280 nm					
16.90	39.84	15.67	48.78	14.86	58.48
13.50	32.58	12.58	39.54	11.90	48.07
11.85	28.32	9.86	31.45	9.31	38.76
10.63	25.58	7.70	27.55	8.33	34.96
8.69	22.52	7.45	24.63	7.45	31.25
7.75	20.06	6.80	22.73	6.45	27.70
7.34	18.22	6.06	20.41	6.05	25.64
Salicylic acid λ_{max} 286 nm					
62.12	99.02	56.82	116.30	52.62	140.84
50.51	86.20	45.73	101.00	44.59	121.95
40.32	68.48	36.02	83.66	35.10	98.04
35.22	60.98	32.68	70.42	30.49	86.20
30.49	53.76	28.25	62.50	26.41	75.45
25.51	44.25	23.98	54.55	21.75	65.50
20.32	35.48	18.45	42.91	17.14	54.94

when all the sites in the silicone rubber are filled and c is the residual concentration of the acid in the solution at equilibrium. Plots of $1/q$ vs $1/C$ (Fig. 1) should be linear and from intercepts saturation values S may be calculated.

To gain an insight into the attractive forces between the various compounds and the polymer, standard affinity values ($-\Delta\mu^\circ$) were calculated using the following equations:

$$S^\circ = \frac{C_S}{C_L}$$

$$-\Delta\mu^\circ = RT \ln \frac{C_S}{C_L} = RT \ln S^\circ \quad \dots (2)$$

S° is the solubility coefficient relating the quantity of solute in the solid phase to the quantity of solute in the liquid phase; C_S is the equilibrium concentration of the solute in the solid phase in

Fig. 1. Langmuir isotherms of (a) Benzoic acid, (b) Salicylic acid.

moles/0.25 gm, and C_L is the equilibrium concentration of the solute in the liquid phase in moles/litre. In a relatively narrow temperature range, the standard affinity is related to standard heat of adsorption (ΔH°) through the equation shown below:

$$\frac{\Delta\mu^\circ}{T} = \frac{\Delta H^\circ}{T} + C \quad (3)$$

where all the terms are as previously defined while C stands for a constant of integration. Heat of sorption for each of the compounds is calculated from the slope of the line obtained by plotting $\Delta\mu^\circ/T$ vs $1/T$ (Fig. 2).

Since the standard affinity, $\Delta\mu^\circ$, may be considered as a change in free energy as the solute migrates from the solution to the solid phase (polymer), it follows that entropy (ΔS°) of sorption may be evaluated through the thermodynamic relationship

$$\Delta\mu^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \quad \dots (4)$$

Table 2 summarises the calculated values of solubility coefficient, saturation values, standard

TABLE 2—SOLUBILITY CO-EFFICIENT, STANDARD AFFINITY, STANDARD HEAT OF SORPTION, STANDARD ENTROPY CHANGE OF SORPTION AND SATURATION VALUE OF BENZOIC ACID AND ITS DERIVATIVES, SILICONE RUBBER BEING USED AS SUBSTRATE

Range of acid concn. (M/L)	Temp. °C	Solubility coefficient 'S' M/O.25 gm/M/L	$\Delta\mu^\circ$ K cal/mole	$-\Delta H^\circ$ K cal/mole	$-\Delta S^\circ$ K cal/mole	Saturation value 'S' $\times 10^3$ M/O. 25 gm	Solubility in gm/1000 cc of water
Benzoic acid-polymer system							
8.43-21.41 $\times 10^{-4}$	15	0.395	0.593			0.179	2.70
	25	0.382	0.754	3.54	0.014	0.249	
	40	0.222	0.942			0.636	
Salicylic acid-polymer system							
2.62-7.75 $\times 10^{-4}$	15	0.560	0.384			0.648	1.80
	25	0.425	0.510	3.94	0.015	0.835	
	40	0.308	0.738			0.883	
<i>m</i> -nitrobenzoic acid-polymer system							
5.95-20.01 $\times 10^{-4}$	15	0.254	0.789			0.1915	0.24
	25	0.218	0.909	3.12	0.014	0.1455	
	40	0.165	1.130			0.2925	
<i>p</i> -nitrobenzoic acid-polymer system							
5.83-14.44 $\times 10^{-4}$	15	0.419	0.501			0.0988	3.10
	25	0.350	0.625	3.23	0.013	0.1053	
	40	0.310	0.734			0.4777	
<i>m</i> -iodobenzoic acid-polymer system							
9.42-16.66 $\times 10^{-4}$	15	0.271	0.752			0.039	0.12
	25	0.241	0.849	3.06	0.013	0.127	
	40	0.196	1.023			0.205	
<i>o</i> -toluic acid-polymer system							
2.99-8.67 $\times 10^{-4}$	15	0.368	0.576			0.218	1.18
	25	0.315	0.691	3.42	0.014	0.467	
	40	0.250	0.867			0.431	
<i>m</i> -toluic acid-polymer system							
8.40-19.02 $\times 10^{-4}$	15	0.247	0.878			0.397	0.85
	25	0.193	0.980	3.19	0.014	0.437	
	40	0.153	1.177			0.681	
<i>p</i> -toluic acid-polymer system							
8.02-23.15 $\times 10^{-4}$	15	0.232	0.841			0.0184	0.34
	25	0.184	1.010	3.59	0.015	0.0391	
	40	0.134	1.261			0.1034	
<i>o</i> -bromobenzoic acid-polymer system							
1.79-6.03 $\times 10^{-4}$	15	0.174	0.956			0.069	1.80
	25	0.156	1.109	2.92	0.014	0.480	
	40	0.122	1.315			0.661	
<i>p</i> -benzoxybenzoic acid-polymer system							
1.30-4.20 $\times 10^{-4}$	15	0.318	0.660			0.0314	—
	25	0.246	0.897	3.81	0.016	0.167	
	40	0.192	1.033			0.098	
<i>m</i> -aminobenzoic acid-polymer system							
1.92-3.99 $\times 10^{-4}$	15	0.206	0.910			0.339	5.90
	25	0.171	1.052	2.94	0.013	0.610	
	40	0.154	1.227			0.730	
<i>m</i> -chlorobenzoic acid-polymer system							
3.98-8.12 $\times 10^{-4}$	15	0.472	1.503			0.209	0.40
	25	0.418	1.803	3.34	0.017	0.486	
	40	0.322	2.466			0.934	
<i>o</i> -chlorobenzoic acid-polymer system							
1.32-8.55 $\times 10^{-4}$	15	0.212	0.893			0.140	2.10
	25	0.198	0.966	2.85	0.013	0.571	
	40	0.147	1.199				
<i>p</i> -chlorobenzoic acid-polymer system							
2.26-8.23 $\times 10^{-4}$	15	0.285	0.723			0.118	0.077
	25	0.230	0.876	3.98	0.016	0.156	
	40	0.151	1.188			0.513	
<i>p</i> -bromobenzoic acid-polymer system							
3.79-8.95 $\times 10^{-4}$	15	0.315	0.665			0.309	0.056
	25	0.250	0.834	3.68	0.015	0.734	
	40	0.209	0.979			0.822	
<i>p</i> -isopropylbenzoic acid-polymer system							
2.36-8.62 $\times 10^{-4}$	15	0.262	0.778			0.035	0.15
	25	0.207	0.939	3.12	0.014	0.038	
	40	0.187	1.121			0.034	

Fig. 2. Plot of $\frac{\Delta\mu^\circ}{T}$ vs $\frac{1}{T}$

- (i) *m*-iodobenzoic acid, (ii) *p*-isopropylbenzoic acid, (iii) *o*-toluic acid, (iv) *m*-toluic acid, (v) *p*-toluic acid, (vi) *p*-bromobenzoic acid, (vii) *o*-bromobenzoic acid, (viii) *m*-aminobenzoic acid.

affinity, heat of sorption and entropy of sorption values for sixteen different compounds at each of the temperature studied.

Discussion

When kept in prolonged contact with insoluble silicone rubber polymer each of the acids studied was sorbed in varying degrees. According to Autian it is apparent that depending on the concentration range studied, different sorption isotherm may result. Therefore, exact interpretation of the result is difficult. Examination of Table 2 in which the solubility coefficients for the sixteen different compounds in the polymer are given show that *p*-chlorobenzoic acid, *m*-nitrobenzoic acid, *p*-isopropylbenzoic acid, *m*-toluic acid, *p*-toluic acid and *m*-iodobenzoic acid have almost similar values; salicylic acid and *m*-chlorobenzoic acid being somewhat more soluble in the silicone rubber. Solubility of compounds in the polymer phase is seen to be markedly influenced by the hydrophobic bonding. In ortho compound except *o*-toluic acid, however, steric factor plays the important role, and due to chelation hydrogen bonding with solvent water as well as with the silicone linkage is hindered and hence the solubility values are lowered. In almost all cases variation of solubility coefficient was observed with the variation of temperature leading to the suggestion that the binding process between the polymer and solutes is temperature dependent; with increased temperature serving to hinder solute-plastic binding.

Standard affinity may be considered as the ability of the particular substrate to attract and hold solute molecules. It is interesting to note that standard affinity values for all the compounds came out as negative values giving an indication of the preference of these acids for the water phase over

the solid phase. In most cases the standard affinity decreases with increasing temperature leading to suggest that the binding force involved in the acid-silicone rubber interaction is predominantly of hydrogen bond type.

Several suggestions concerning the mechanism of interaction between the acids and the silicone rubber can be made from the examination of the standard heats of sorption values for these solutes sorbed by the rubber. In regard to the compounds under investigation it is seen that the standard heats of sorption range from 2.85 to 3.98 K cal/mole formulating an energy requirement basis for the formation of hydrogen bonds between these acids and the polymer⁹. Presumably bonding in the case of the acids would occur between the carboxyl group of the acid and the oxygen atom in the silicone linkage of the polymer chain. Molecular weight of the acids has also got an important role on the strength of the interaction; with the increase of molecular weight a definite increase in some cases could be seen in the strength of the interaction. It may be concluded that the net attractive forces between the acids and the silicone linkage of the polymer may be related with the solubilities and the molecular weight of the compounds studied.

A consideration of the experimental values for the standard entropies of sorption for these compounds may throw further light on the binding process. The probability of a combination occurring between solute and the substrate can be interpreted from the entropy values, giving a direct relation between the probability and the increase in entropy. The greater the increase in entropy greater will be the probability of combination between the interactants. For the *m*-chlorobenzoic acid though the ΔH is not so higher, relatively higher entropy value indicates the greater probability of interaction with the polymer which is also reflected in low water solubilities. Standard entropies of sorption (Table 2) of a given system also determine the possible sites of binding or interaction for sixteen different acids with the specific polymer studied.

References

1. A. J. CAPADIA, W. L. GUESS and J. AUTIAN, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1964, **53**, 720.
2. H. F. BERG, W. L. GUESS and J. AUTIAN, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1965, **54**, 79.
3. M. B. RODRIGUEZ, R. BORDNAR and W. L. GUESS, 1965, **54**, 129; 1966, **55**, 1429.
4. J. AUTIAN, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1963, **51**, 1.
5. E. MARCUS, H. K. KHIM and J. AUTIAN, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc. Sci. Edn.*, 1959, **48**, 457.
H. K. KHIM and J. AUTIAN, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc. Sci. Edn.*, 1960, **49**, 227.
6. R. D. SCHOENWALD and P. F. BRICASTRO, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1969, **58**, 930.

7. M. B. RODELL, W. L. GUESS and J. AUTIAN, 1964, *J. Chem. Phys.*, **53**, 873.
8. N. K. PATEL and N. NAGABHUSHAN, *J. Pharm. Edn.*, 1969, **33**, 392.
9. A. M. BEYERLEIN, B. S. SHETH and J. AUTIAN, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1971, **60**, 1317.
10. R. F. BLANKS and J. M. PRANSNITZ, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1963, **38**, 1500.
11. J. HEILL and J. M. PRANSNITZ, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1966, **44**, 737.
12. C. G. OSTER, *J. Poly. Sci.*, 1955, **16**, 235.
13. G. W. C. HUNG and J. AUTIAN, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1972, **61**, 1094.
14. G. W. C. HUNG, L. J. NUNEZ and J. AUTIAN, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1973, **62**, 1308.
15. S. MUKHERJEE, S. K. DE and S. R. PALIT, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 270.